

Particulate emissions of heavy duty diesel engines measured from the tailpipe and the dilution tunnel

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ABSTRACT

In China particulate matter (PM) is the leading environmental risk factor to morbidity and mortality, with transport being the main source of PM pollution in cities. China VI emission limit standards, which are one of the most stringent worldwide, have only recently been introduced and there is lack of studies assessing the PM emissions of new engines. In Europe, there are discussions ongoing to permit sampling directly from the tailpipe with fixed dilution for determining the solid particle number (SPN) emissions during type approval of heavy duty engines; something that is practically allowed for on-road testing. In this study the particulate emissions of seven engines were measured. Three of them were fulfilling the China VI limits, two China V, while two of them were China III engines retrofitted with diesel particulate filters (DPFs). One system with evaporation tube was installed at the full dilution tunnel, as prescribed in the regulation, and another one with catalytic stripper was sampling from the tailpipe, both measuring >23 nm and >10 nm particles. The results showed a wide range of particulate emission levels depending on the engine, the existence of a DPF, the connection point of the crankcase ventilation, and the occurrence of active or passive regeneration. The system at the tailpipe measured on average 20% lower than the system at the dilution tunnel. The system at the dilution tunnel measured much higher during one regeneration due to re-nucleation of volatiles downstream of the evaporation tube. For one engine, the emissions of the evaporation tube system were more than double when the crankcase ventilation was connected downstream of the aftertreatment devices. The main message from this study is that a catalytic stripper is necessary for sub-23 nm measurements and tailpipe sampling with fixed dilution is a plausible option.

1. Introduction

Air pollution is a major threat to health and climate. Ambient air pollution accounts for an estimated 4.2 million deaths per year due to stroke, heart disease, lung cancer, acute and chronic respiratory diseases (WHO, 2018). As one of the most important air pollution sources, particulate matter (PM) has been rated at the top five risk factors on human health and the leading environmental risk factor to morbidity and mortality in China (Zhou et al., 2019). Several studies have shown that PM health effects depend on composition, particle size, and particle origin (Dergham et al., 2015; Longhin et al., 2020). Long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} (PM < 2.5 μm) exceeding

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the WHO limit ($10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ -annual average) can increase the risk of cardiovascular disease by approximately 11% (Hoek et al., 2013).

In China, the number of motor vehicles has surged from 5 million to 310 million since the 1990s (National Bureau of Statistics of the People's Republic of China, 2018). Approximately 44 million tons of pollutants are emitted from motor vehicles each year (MEEC, 2018a). More importantly, vehicle emissions can greatly promote secondary air pollutants (Anenberg et al., 2017). The official source allocation results of China's pollution indicate that mobile source emissions have become the main source of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations in several cities (Wu et al., 2017). Therefore, mitigating vehicle emissions has become one of the most important tasks related to air pollution control. The State Council of China launched the "Three-Year Action Plan for Winning the Blue Sky Defense Battle" in 2018 to accelerate the improvement of ambient air quality (MEEC, 2018b). Heavy-duty diesel vehicle account for only a small portion of motor vehicles, but make an important contribution to the emission of PM (Biswas et al., 2008; Wagner & Rutherford, 2013). The action plan clearly requires more effective emission management for heavy-duty diesel vehicles. Stringent emission standards have forced major technological improvements in diesel vehicle aftertreatment systems, especially in reducing PM emissions. There are some studies that have examined the emissions of older engines (Ma et al., 2018), but the information for China V and China VI engines are limited without any information on particle number emissions (Jin et al., 2018; Li & Lü, 2021). However, with the advances of engine and aftertreatment technology, the PM mass limit could no longer meet the purpose of limiting emissions; consequently, the introduction of a number limit was necessary. The latest China VI emission standard (GB 17691-2018) tightened the emission limit requirements for PM. Under the transient cycle, the China V limit of PM mass from 2.0 g/kWh dropped to 0.01 g/kWh, and a solid particle number (SPN) emission limit of 6.0×10^{11} p/kWh was introduced ("p" is used for particles in this paper). The implementation of the China VI standards for heavy-duty vehicles started recently: July 2019 for new gas vehicles, July 2020 for new urban vehicles, July 2021 for the remaining. China VI-b took effect on January 2021 for new gas vehicles, and from July 2023 for all new vehicles.

The regulated SPN methodology measures solid particles with size >23 nm. The SPN systems have an evaporation tube at 350°C to remove volatiles and a condensation particle counter (CPC) that counts the particles with 50% detection efficiency at 23 nm. Recent studies found high concentrations of sub-23 nm particles for heavy duty compressed natural gas (CNG) (Giechaskiel, 2018; Lehtoranta et al., 2017) or even diesel engines due to urea injection (Giechaskiel, 2018; Mamakos et al., 2019). There are discussions in Europe to reduce the lower cut-off size of the CPC from 23 nm to approximately 10 nm. Due to the potential volatile artefacts (i.e. re-nucleation of volatiles downstream of the evaporation tube), a catalytic stripper is necessary for sub-23 nm measurements (Giechaskiel, Melas, et al., 2020). Another topic of interest in Europe is the possibility to use SPN systems directly at the tailpipe to measure the emissions, without a proportional partial flow system or a full dilution tunnel (Giechaskiel, Lähde, et al., 2019). This is stemmed from the fact that SPN measurements are already allowed from the tailpipe for in-use testing with portable emissions measurement systems (PEMS) (Giechaskiel, Bonnel, et al., 2019).

The objectives of this paper are: (i) to study the PM mass and SPN emissions of engines at different China stages, (ii) to assess the need of decreasing the lower size of 23 nm–10 nm, and (iii) to investigate the possibility of using direct tailpipe sampling for SPN measurements. The same "Golden" instruments that were used in a similar exercise in Europe (Giechaskiel, Lähde, et al., 2019) were used in this study.

2. Materials and methods

The experiments were conducted at the Xiamen Environment Protection Vehicle Emission Control Technology Center (VETC). VETC is China's national public service platform approved by the Ministry of Ecology and Environment of China. It is a testing

Fig. 1. Schematic of the experimental setup. CPC = condensation particle counter; CS = catalytic Stripper; CVS = constant volume sampling; EEPS = engine exhaust particle sizer; ET = evaporation tube; PM = particulate matter; VPR = volatile particle remover.

organization researching advanced vehicle emission control technologies with international certification capabilities and represents China in foreign exchanges and cooperation. At the same time, it is also a platform and cooperating unit for the preliminary preparation of national laws and policies.

2.1. Experimental setup

The typical experimental setup is given in Fig. 1. Different engines with various aftertreatment devices were tested for their particulate emissions (see details in Table 1). The exhaust gas was diluted in a dilution tunnel with constant volume sampling (CVS). The flow rate was set to 20–120 m³/min, depending on the engine displacement (2–10.7 L). A small flow of 15–30 L/min was extracted from the CVS via a hatted probe and passed through a filter in a filter holder; heated to 47 °C only during the China VI engine tests. The expected cut-off size is between 2.5 µm and 10 µm (Giechaskiel, Arndt, et al., 2012). The PM mass emissions were determined gravimetrically by weighing the filter before and after the test. The filters were 47 mm teflon-coated glass-fiber Pallflex TX40HI20WW filters.

The solid particle number (SPN) emissions were measured in real time with an AVL (Graz, Austria) particle counter (APC 489) (Giechaskiel et al., 2010). It consisted of Volatile Particle Remover (VPR) and two Condensation Particle Counters (CPCs). The VPR consisted of a hot diluter at 150 °C, an evaporation tube at 350 °C, and a secondary dilution at ambient temperature. One of the CPCs had 50% counting efficiency at 23 nm (TSI 3790, Shoreview, MN, USA), and the other one 65% counting efficiency at 10 nm (TSI 3792). This system will be called as “CVS(ET)”.

Another APC was used at the tailpipe, in order to investigate the equivalency of tailpipe PN measurements with the CVS measurements. The differences of this system to the other APC at the CVS were: (i) it had a catalytic stripper (Amanatidis et al., 2013) instead of an evaporation tube, (ii) a 0.5 m stainless steel heated line (at 150 °C) was used to connect it to the tailpipe. This system will be called as “TP(CS)”. This system and the 10 nm CPC of the CVS(ET) were provided by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission (EU) and were used at the European investigation of the SPN tailpipe measurements (Giechaskiel, Lähde, et al., 2019).

For a limited number of tests with one engine (#7) an engine exhaust particle size (EEPS) was available measuring from the dilution tunnel (CVS) total particles (i.e. solids and volatiles). The EEPS measured size distributions in the range 5.6 nm–560 nm based on electrical charging, size classification in a column with electric field, and counting with electrometers (Wang et al., 2016).

2.2. Engines and fuel

The engines and aftertreatment devices covered a wide range (Table 1): The smallest was a 2.0 L engine and the largest 10.7 L. The oldest were China III type approved (#1, #2), but retrofitted with a diesel particulate filter (DPF). The latest China VI (#5, #6, #7) had aftertreatment system that included a diesel oxidation catalyst (DOC), selective catalytic reduction for NO_x (SCR), ammonia slip catalyst (ASC) and DPF. One of the China V engines had no DPF (#3), while one other was tested with and without the aftertreatment devices (which included a DPF) (#4).

The fuel used for the China III and China V engines was reference China V diesel fuel with density 835.1 kg/m³, cetane number 52.4, 9.4 ppm sulfur level, and 3.3% (m/m). For the China VI engines, reference China VI fuel was used with density 830.4 kg/m³, cetane number 52.5, 8.3 ppm sulfur level, and 1.9% (m/m).

2.3. Test protocol

The tests were mainly the cold and hot start WHTC (Worldwide harmonized transient cycle) and hot start WHSC (Worldwide harmonized stationary cycle). Hot start ETC (European transient cycle) and ESC (European stationary cycle) were also conducted for older engines. Additional cycles, such NRTC (Non-road transient cycle), NRSC (Non-road stationary cycle) and FLC (Full load curve) were also conducted to cover a wide range of operation conditions of the engine map and transient conditions. The number of tests for

Table 1

Characteristics of the compression ignition (diesel) engines of this study. Aftertreatment devices are presented in order from engine outlet, except #6 for which the order is not known.

	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	#7
Emission stand.	III	III	V	V	VI	VI	VI
No. cylinders	6	4	6	4	4	6	4
Displacement [L]	8.4	5.2	9.8	2.8	2.3	10.7	2.0
Max power [kW] (rpm)	228 (2200)	128 (2300)	254 (1900)	110 (2900)	93 (3200)	335 (1600)	88 (3200)
Max torque [Nm] (rpm)	1150 (1400)	660 (1400)	1660 (1100–1400)	360 (1500–2000)	380 (1600–2400)	2200 (1100)	350 (1600–2400)
After-treatment	DOC	DOC	SCR	DOC	DOC	DOC	DOC
	DPF/R	DPF/R	ASC	DPF	SCR	SCR	SCR
					ASC	ASC	ASC
					DPF	DPF	DPF

ASC = ammonia slip catalyst; DPF = diesel particulate filter; DPF/R = diesel Particulate filter (retrofitted); DOC = diesel oxidation catalyst; SCR = selective catalytic reduction for NO_x.

each engine is given in Table 2. Dedicated tests were conducted to see the effect of regeneration, urea injection from the SCR, and crankcase ventilation on the SPN emissions. As mentioned before, engines #1 and #2 were tested without any aftertreatment devices or with the retrofit system (DOC and DPF). Engines #4, #6, and #7 were tested with and without their aftertreatment devices. In the text, the term filtration efficiency in addition to the DPF, includes the removal of particles from the DOC, SCR and ASC when present, but their filtration efficiency should be very low and practically is the DPF filtration efficiency.

For a few tests both APCs were connected to the CVS in order to check their differences (Instrumentation in Table 2). The comparison of the instruments will not be presented. An example is given in Appendix, Fig. A1. In general, the 23 nm CPCs were within 5% and the 10 nm CPCs within 10%, when measuring above their background levels ($>1 \text{ p/cm}^3$).

2.4. Calculations

The PM mass and CVS SPN >23 results were given by the automation system. Nevertheless, the CVS SPN >23 and SPN >10 were re-calculated by multiplying the 23 nm CPC and the 10 nm CPC concentrations with their respective calibration factors, the particle concentration reduction factor (PCRF) of the VPR (which combines dilution and mean losses) (typically 500–2000), and the CVS flow rate. The sum was then divided by the engine work. The re-calculated SPN >23 results were within 1% from the reported values from the automation system. The tailpipe SPN results were calculated synchronizing the tailpipe CPC signals with the exhaust flow rate, then multiplying the CPC concentrations with their calibration factors, the PCRF (typically 500–2000) and the exhaust flow rate. The exhaust flow rate was the sum of the intake air and fuel flow rates. The sum was then divided by the exhaust gas density and the engine work. Details about the equations can be found elsewhere (Giechaskiel, Lähde, & Drossinos, 2019).

The accuracy of the PM mass measurements can be on the order of 0.1 mg/kWh (based on the 1 μg balance accuracy), however due to volatile artefacts on the TX40 filters is on the order of 1 mg/kWh (Giechaskiel, Mamakos, et al., 2012; Högström et al., 2012; Maricq et al., 2011).

Regarding the SPN systems, recently a theoretical study estimated an expanded uncertainty of 34% and 42% when sampling from the tailpipe for >23 nm and >10 nm systems (Giechaskiel et al., 2021). The major contributors to the uncertainty were the calibration uncertainty (13–18%), the size uncertainty (25–36%), the particle losses (12–14%), and the exhaust flow rate (5%). In our case we cross-checked the two particle counters and the differences were within 5–10%. The exhaust flow rate determined by intake air and fuel was 5% less compared to the flow rate determined by CO_2 measurements at the dilution tunnel and the tailpipe (thus the tailpipe results might be underestimating the emissions). Since the systems were from the same instrument manufacturer, the size uncertainty should be lower than 25–36%. Thus, the total SPN uncertainty should be closer to the uncertainty reported for commercial systems in that study (15–17%).

In the graphs the concentrations of particles with sizes >23 nm (SPN_{23}) and/or >10 nm (SPN_{10}) are separately given. When the two are compared the sub-23 nm percentage (i.e. 10 nm–23 nm concentration compared to >23 nm concentration) is calculated as:

$$\text{Sub-23 nm} = (\text{SPN}_{10} - \text{SPN}_{23}) / \text{SPN}_{23} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

3. Results

3.1. Emission levels

The PM mass emissions (cut-off size between 2.5 μm and 10 μm) of the seven engines are summarized in Fig. 2. The engines without DPF (#3, #4) had emissions between 6 mg/kWh and 26 mg/kWh, while engine #7 emitted around 35 mg/kWh at the hot cycles when the whole aftertreatment system was removed. The China VI engines with DPF (#5, #6, #7) emitted <1.6 mg/kWh under all tests. The China III retrofitted engines (#1, #2) emitted around 4 mg/kWh, except engine #1 which emitted 75 mg/kWh at the cold WHTC. Their engine out emissions were >100 mg/kWh, exceeding 400 mg/kWh at the cold cycle with engine #1.

The DPF filtration efficiency based on tests with and without aftertreatment device was $>95.5\%$ for all engines tested (#1, #2, #7) except for the cold cycle of engine #1 (85%). However, the filtration efficiency for the combined WHTC (weighted 14% for the cold WHTC and 86% for the hot WHTC) was 92%.

Fig. 3 summarizes the SPN emissions determined with the CVS(ET) system. The engines without DPF (#3, #4) had emissions between 1.5 and 6×10^{13} p/kWh, while engine #7 emitted 12×10^{13} p/kWh at the hot WHTC when the DPF was removed. The China

Table 2

Number of total tests per engine and additional investigations. Y = yes; N = no; w = with; w/o = without

	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	#7
Total tests	7	13	11	14	8	118	23
With and w/o aftertreatment	Y	Y	w/o	Y	w	w	Y
Regeneration	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y
Crankcase emissions	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y
With and w/o urea injection	–	N	Y	–	N	N	Y
Instrumentation	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	N

Fig. 2. PM mass emissions. Error bars show the max value of two or three repetitions (when available). DPF = diesel particulate filter; T_c = cold start WHTC; T_h = hot start WHTC (ETC for #3); S=WHSC (ESC for #3).

VI engines with DPF (#5, #6, #7) emitted $<6 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh under all tests. The China III retrofitted engines (#1, #2) emitted around 4×10^{11} p/kWh at the hot cycles, and $2-6 \times 10^{12}$ p/kWh at the cold WHTCs.

The sub-23 nm percentage (Eq. 1), i.e. the 10–23 nm to >23 nm particle concentration ratios were 17–59% for the non-DPF engines, 4–34% for the DPF equipped engines with emissions $>1 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh, but 61–153% with emissions $<1 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh. High sub-23 nm percentages were found during cold start and with urea injection (Appendix, Fig. A2). The contribution of sub-23 nm particles was high in relative terms when the absolute emissions were low ($<1 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh).

The filtration efficiency based on tests with and without aftertreatment devices was $>97.5\%$ for all engines tested (#1, #2, #4, #7), and slightly higher for >10 nm particles ($>98.2\%$). The higher filtration efficiency for smaller particles is expected due to the higher diffusion of smaller particles (Dorscheidt et al., 2020).

3.2. TP(CS) vs. CVS(ET)

The comparison of the system at the tailpipe with catalytic stripper to the system at the CVS with evaporation tube is given in Fig. 4a for SPN >23 nm and Fig. 4b for SPN >10 nm. Regenerations and tests with the crankcase ventilation connected to the tailpipe were not included, because they will be discussed separately in the next sections.

For emission levels $>6 \times 10^{10}$ p/kWh the TP(CS) was measuring 0–40% less than the CVS(ET), with a mean difference of 20%, for both >23 nm and >10 nm. At lower concentrations the differences were higher, due to the higher particle background of the CVS (see Appendix, Fig. A3). The difference could not be attributed to calibration of the systems, because when they were both measuring at the CVS, they were within $\pm 10\%$ (Appendix, Fig. A1).

Fig. 3. SPN emissions of seven engines (#1-#7) for various cycles determined with the CVS(ET) system. Some engines had no DPF or the complete aftertreatment including the DPF was removed (w/o DPF). Number give the percentage of 10–23 nm particle concentrations to >23 nm particle concentrations (Eq. 1). Error bars show the max value of two or three repetitions (when available). T_c = cold start WHTC; T_h = hot start WHTC (ETC hot for #3); S=WHSC (ESC for #3).

Fig. 4. Comparisons of solid particle number (SPN) emissions >23 nm as measured with the system at the dilution tunnel CVS(ET) and the system at the tailpipe TP(CS) for the various engines: (a) > 23 nm; (b) > 10 nm.

3.3. Regeneration

Fig. 5a presents the emissions during one passive regeneration with engine #2, and two active regenerations with engines #6 and #7. The results are plotted separately for the catalytic stripper system at the tailpipe TP(CS) and the evaporation tube system at the dilution tunnel CV(ET). Compared to the non-regenerating hot WHTCs (shown with dotted lines) the emissions increased 2–3 orders of magnitude during the active regenerations. They reached 2–5 × 10¹² p/kWh, exceeding the SPN limit of 6 × 10¹¹ p/kWh. The sub-23 nm particles were 7–20% of the >23 nm levels, with one exception with the CVS (ET) system (46%) that is plotted in Fig. 5b. The two systems with the 23 nm and 10 nm counters were close to each other until 750 s, where the CVS(ET) 10 nm concentration started to deviate, until approximately 900 s. This is a clear indication of re-nucleation downstream of the evaporation tube (volatile artifact) (Giechaskiel, Melas, et al., 2020). When the fuel post injection stopped (around time 820 s) (and the regeneration) (Rothe et al., 2015), the SPN concentration dropped, while the CVS(ET) 10 nm system at the dilution tunnel continued to measure high concentrations.

3.4. Crankcase emissions

Fig. 6a compares the catalytic stripper system at the tailpipe TP(CS) with the evaporation tube system at the dilution tunnel CVS (ET), when both were measuring the crankcase emissions. The crankcase ventilation was connected downstream of the aftertreatment devices, but upstream of the TP(CS) system. For engine #2 a silicone non-heated tube was used, while for engine #6 a metallic bellows heated tube at 95 °C. Starting with engine #6, the ratio of the two systems was <30% with or without the crankcase emissions and increased at lower emission levels, in agreement with the typical tests presented in Fig. 4. This means that the crankcase emissions could be thermally treated efficiently with the evaporation tube system. With engine #2, there was a big difference (>100%) between the two systems when the crankcase emissions were connected to the tailpipe. Without crankcase emissions, the differences were

Fig. 5. Regeneration emissions: (a) Emissions of three engines (#2, #6, #7) determined with the TP(CS) and CVS(ET) systems. Dotted lines show the SPN levels of hot WHTCs; (b) Real time regeneration emissions of engine #7 with various SPN systems.

Fig. 6. Crankcase emissions: (a) Comparison of TP(CS) and CVS(ET) systems when both were measuring the crankcase emissions; (b) Comparison of TP(CS) and CVS(ET) systems when only the CVS(ET) was measuring the crankcase emissions.

<30%, but >100% with crankcase emissions. A closer look to the real time measurements of the crankcase signals (Appendix, Fig. A4b) revealed a relatively constant overestimation over the whole cycle, and not a particular time point where re-nucleation downstream of the evaporation tube occurred. In this case, probably due to the non-heated crankcase tube that was used and the high concentration of the crankcase emissions, the particles remained large in size and could not be efficiently reduced in size by the evaporation tube. Consequently, they were measured with high efficiency.

Fig. 6b compares the two systems, but when the crankcase ventilation was connected downstream of the TP(CS) system. Thus, their difference can be attributed to the crankcase emissions. Starting with engine #6, the slope was between 1.18 and 1.25, showing a 18% (>10 nm) to 25% (>23 nm) difference of the two systems TP(CS) and CVS(ET), in agreement with all previous tests (see e.g. Fig. 4). However, there was an offset of 1.18×10^{11} p/kWh (>10 nm) to 1.45×10^{11} p/kWh (>23 nm), which showed the contribution of the crankcase ventilation. For engine #7, there were only a few tests available, which showed a much higher contribution of the crankcase ventilation $3\text{--}4 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh.

4. Discussion

Particulate matter (PM) is the top environmental risk factors on human health in China (Zhou et al., 2019). PM also causes damage to ecosystems and cultural sites, and reduced visibility. Ultrafine particles (smaller than 100 nm) are also associated with adverse health effects (Ohlwein et al., 2019). On one hand, due to their higher deposition fraction, deeper penetration and higher retention in the lungs, on the other, due to their translocation from the lungs to other organs, such as the heart or the brain (Kwon et al., 2020). Thus, both PM mass and particle number emission standards are important to control the impact of engines on air pollution (Giechaskiel et al., 2009).

This is one of the first studies to report emissions from China VI engines. Both PM mass and SPN emissions were well below the respective limits (10 mg/kWh and 6×10^{11} p/kWh) for all three China VI engines. These results are in agreement with Euro VI heavy-duty engines with the same PM mass and SPN limits (Giechaskiel, 2018). The PM mass emissions of the two China V engines were below the applicable limit for the transient cycle (30 mg/kWh). The filtration efficiencies of the four evaluated DPFs (two original and two retrofitted) were >95% for PM mass and >97.5% for SPN; typical filtration efficiencies of DPFs reported in the literature (Fleischman et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2012; Quan-shun et al., 2017; Tartakovsky et al., 2015). The only exception was the low filtration efficiency for PM mass (85%) of the retrofitted DPF of China III engine #1 for the cold start cycle. The filtration efficiency for SPN was still >97.5%. High particulate levels at cold start for DPF-equipped engines have been attributed to small leaks at the mat connecting the filter to the canister, which close up as the filter heats up (Mamakos et al., 2013). Nevertheless, this China III retrofitted engine would meet the China V limit (using 14% weight factor for the cold start cycle, and 86% of the hot start cycle). The other retrofitted engine could even meet the China VI PM limit. Similarly, the China VI SPN limit could be met only by one of the retrofitted engines; the other engine's weighted SPN emission were 2 times higher than the SPN limit.

Active regenerations increased the SPN emissions 2 orders of magnitude, while passive regeneration 2–3 times. Similar conclusions about regeneration emissions have been reached by others (Giechaskiel, 2018; Smith et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2017; Yamada et al., 2017) and have been attributed to the low filtration efficiency of the DPF during the few minutes during and after the regeneration, when it's empty.

Correlation of PM mass with SPN >23 nm gave the expected slope (3×10^{12} p/mg) only for the non-DPF equipped engines (Fig. 7a). Correlation factors of 2×10^{12} p/mg are commonly reported in the literature (Giechaskiel, Mamakos, et al., 2012). For the DPF equipped engines the slope was very low (8×10^{10} p/mg). Interestingly there was a good correlation ($R^2 = 0.91$), but this was due to the high emissions point (75 mg/kWh) of engine #1. Removing this point, the correlation got worse ($R^2 = 0.41$) and the slope increased to 2×10^{11} p/mg. Not forcing the slope through the zero, would result in a PM offset of 0.3 mg/kWh. The slope remained low, but such

values have been reported for low emitting vehicles with or without DPF (Giechaskiel, Woodburn, et al., 2020). The reason of such low slopes was the high amount of volatiles collected on the filter. Hydrocarbons adsorption on the filter can also influence the mass result on the order of 1 mg/kWh (Högström et al., 2012). At the 1 mg/kWh range, PM-SPN correlation factors should be avoided, due to their high scatter, and the two metric should be treated separately. The figure also includes the DPF equipped engines (#2, #6, #7) that were tested connecting the crankcase ventilation to the tailpipe. Although no correlation is given for these points, their slope is similar to the rest DPF points. For engines #6 and #7 the levels remained similar (and lower than 4 mg/kWh), while for engine #2 they clearly increased from approximately 4 mg/kWh to 17 mg/kWh.

Fig. 7b plots the solid (>10 nm) and total (volatiles and solids) (>6 nm) emissions of engine #7, with and without DPF. The total emissions were determined with an engine exhaust particle sizer (EEPS) at the dilution tunnel (Wang et al., 2016). The total emissions were 39% higher than the solid emissions for the non-DPF case; a difference which indicates no nucleation mode particles considering the different principles of the instruments used and the different lower detection sizes. However, for the DPF case, the total emissions were more than three orders of magnitude higher than the solid emissions clearly indicating volatile nucleation mode particles. Nucleation mode particles downstream of DPFs are commonly reported (Wang et al., 2017; Zheng et al., 2011). It has been argued though that desorption from the tube that connects the engine to the dilution tunnel contributes significantly to the growth of these nucleation mode particles (Giechaskiel, 2020; Maricq et al., 2017). Although these are values for the WHSC and there are no repetitions available, these results confirm the high contribution of volatiles on the PM filter when no DPF is present.

The sub-23 nm SPN emissions were <60% of the SPN >23 nm emissions for non-DPF engines, in agreement with the literature (Giechaskiel, 2018). Higher percentages (>60%) were found for low emission levels ($<1 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh), thus a significant part of the emitted particles is not counted for these engines, indicating that the measurement from >10 nm is more appropriate. High sub-23 nm particle concentrations were identified (i) during the first 200 s of cold start, and (ii) when the SCR was active (urea particles). Details are given in the Appendix, Fig. A2. Both cases are well known in the literature (Giechaskiel, 2018, 2020). Furthermore, for non DPF-equipped engines, due to the higher concentrations, agglomeration of particles increases their sizes and subsequently reduces the sub-23 nm fraction. Although the sub-23 nm percentages were quite high, there were only three cases that an engine would pass the 6×10^{11} p/kWh limit with the >23 nm system, but fail with the >10 nm system. A lower future PN limit at the 1×10^{11} p/kWh with a lower size of 10 nm, as discussed in EU, would be challenging for some of the China VI engines of this study and Euro VI engines reported elsewhere (Giechaskiel, Lähde, et al., 2019).

One of the important findings of this study was the difference between the tailpipe and the dilution tunnel SPN systems. In this study the tailpipe system was always lower than the dilution tunnel system, with an average difference of 20%. The differences can be attributed to the different penetration curves of the two systems, and the higher sampling losses of the tailpipe system. Such differences were not found at the European inter-laboratory exercise with similar instrumentation, where the differences were within $\pm 25\%$. The main difference of the two studies is that the laboratories in Europe used proportional partial flow systems, while in this study a full dilution system was used. It is possible that the tailpipe systems (either SPN or proportional diluters) have higher particle losses at the sampling lines compared to the full dilution tunnel. For example, cooling of the exhaust gas from 350 °C to 150 °C (temperature at the inlet of the systems) results in 15% losses (Giechaskiel, Arndt, et al., 2012). Furthermore, agglomeration in the sampling lines could further reduce the concentration for the high emitting engines. Another possible explanation is the different thermal pre-treatment of the two systems. The catalytic stripper system at the tailpipe avoided nucleation and condensation in the first place due to the direct sampling with hot dilution. In addition, it oxidized the volatile particles leaving the solid particles without any condensed material. The evaporation tube system at the dilution tunnel could evaporate nucleation mode particles but downstream of the evaporation tube condensation on soot particles was possible. Although there is no information about the amount of volatiles, a few tests with the EEPS showed that they were high for engine #7 (Fig. 7b). Thus, the particles entering the CPC were bigger compared to those entering the

Fig. 7. (a) Correlation between PM mass and SPN >23 nm for all engines (code of engine is given at each point); (b) Solid particle number (SPN) measured with the evaporation tube at the dilution tunnel and total particle number (TPN) emissions measured with an engine exhaust particle sizer (EEPS) at the dilution tunnel (engine #7, with and without DPF, cycle WHSC). GMD = geometric mean diameter.

CPC of the catalytic stripper system. Although this size difference is irrelevant for bigger particles (e.g. >50 nm), it can have a big effect for particles close to the detection limit of the CPCs, or close to the steep part of the penetration curve of the dilution systems. In this study the sub-23 nm particles were typically >60% of those <23 nm, meaning that a high concentration of sub-23 nm particles was present. In any case the differences found in this study are still comparable with a few others that have performed similar comparisons (Khan et al., 2018).

Another different result with the European exercise was that the tailpipe and dilution tunnel systems had differences when crankcase emissions were measured. In the European exercise the two systems were equivalent. In this exercise they were equivalent with one engine (#6) but not with another one (#2). With the second engine (#2) the system at the dilution tunnel was measuring two times higher than the system at the tailpipe, highlighting the need of the catalytic stripper for such measurements. It is not clear whether this is due to the specific engine and the high crankcase emissions or the non-heated tubing that was used to connect the crankcase ventilation to the tailpipe. The gaseous hydrocarbon measurements increased 5–10 mg/kWh (from 5 mg/kWh to 15 mg/kWh) for engine #2, and 5 mg/kWh (from 2 mg/kWh to 7 mg/kWh) for engine #6. The PM mass emissions increased 13 mg/kWh for engine #2 (from 4 mg/kWh to 17 mg/kWh), but remained practically the same for engine #6 (around 1–2 mg/kWh). These results point to the direction that the main reason for this difference of the SPN measurements with engine #2 was due to the high amount of high molecular species not captured by the hydrocarbons measurement (Zielinska et al., 2008). It should be reminded that engine #6 was a China VI engine, and as with the rest European VI engines had to fulfil the limits including the crankcase emissions. Engine #2 was a China III engine without any requirements for the crankcase emissions. In addition to the more challenging concentrations for the evaporation tube system at the dilution tunnel with engine #2, the different penetrations and different final particle sizes probably can explain the difference. The crankcase ventilation emissions contributed around 1.4×10^{11} p/kWh in this exercise, in agreement with the European exercise where a contribution of 2.3×10^{11} p/kWh was found. The increase of the emissions due to the crankcase ventilation is known: Both nucleation and accumulation particles have been found (Bai & Qiao, 2016) with differences depending on the engines (Tatli & Clark, 2008). The important message from these findings is to take into account the crankcase emissions when on-road tests are conducted and the crankcase ventilation is not fed back to the tailpipe for open systems.

Both exercises showed that the measurements of regenerations might result in volatile artefacts for sub-23 nm measurements with systems having only evaporation tube (Giechaskiel, Lähde, et al., 2019). This result is in agreement with the recent literature review on the topic (Giechaskiel, Melas, et al., 2020), and it supports the recent decision to make the catalytic stripper obligatory in sub-23 nm measurements for light-duty vehicles (GTR 15). Similarly, the proposal for sub-23 nm measurements for heavy-duty engines requires catalytic stripper.

5. Conclusions

The particulate matter (PM) mass and number emissions of seven China III-VI heavy-duty diesel engines were measured. The solid particle number (SPN) emissions were determined with one system with catalytic stripper connected at the tailpipe, and one with evaporation tube connected at the full dilution tunnel with constant volume sampling (CVS). Special attention was given to regenerations and crankcase ventilation emissions.

The China VI engines emitted <1.6 mg/kWh and $<6 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh. One China III DPF retrofitted engine had emissions <4 mg/kWh. A second one China III retrofitted engine had 75 mg/kWh cold start emissions, but 3.7 mg/kWh under hot operation. The engine out of these engines were >100 mg/kWh (400 mg/kWh at cold start one of the engines). The SPN emissions of these retrofitted engines were 3.4×10^{11} p/kWh at the hot start cycles, but 2.6×10^{12} p/kWh at the cold start cycles, but the engine out emissions were around 2.5×10^{14} p/kWh. The China V and VI engines without DPF emitted 6–35 mg/kWh and $1.5\text{--}12 \times 10^{13}$ p/kWh. The sub-23 nm particles were <60% compared to the >23 nm particle emissions for non-DPF engines or DPF engines emitting $>1 \times 10^{11}$ p/kWh. They were 60–155% for lower emissions. The emission levels during DPF active regenerations increased >2 orders of magnitude and reached 2.5×10^{12} p/kWh, while passive regeneration increased the emissions 2–3 times reaching 6×10^{11} p/kWh. When the crankcase ventilation was connected to the tailpipe downstream of the aftertreatment devices, the absolute levels of the emissions increased by 1.4×10^{11} p/kWh.

The system connected to the tailpipe with catalytic stripper was measuring on average 20% less than the system at the dilution tunnel with evaporation tube, for both >23 nm and >10 nm measurements. The differences remained relatively constant also during most regeneration events or when measuring crankcase emissions with some exceptions. In one regeneration there was a clear volatile artifact (re-nucleation downstream of the evaporation tube), while with one engine the difference was >100% when crankcase emissions were measured. The difference was attributed to the high crankcase emissions of the specific engine and the different thermal pre-treatment of the exhaust gas from the two systems. The direct hot dilution with catalytic stripper kept the particles in small sizes, and thus they were measured with low efficiency. With the evaporation tube system, the evaporated species condensed on the solid particles and grew them, and thus they were measured with higher efficiency. Furthermore, thermophoretic losses when sampling directly from the tailpipe might have augmented the differences.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, B.G. and S.S.; methodology, T.L.; formal analysis, B.G. and T.L.; writing—original draft preparation, B.G. and T.L.; writing—review and editing, Y.L. and J.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A

Fig. A1 presents real time diluted concentrations at the inlet of the CPCs with the catalytic stripper and evaporation tube systems, when both were connected at the dilution tunnel. The specific test was a hot WHTC with engine #6. The agreement was very good with differences <5% for the 23 nm CPCs and <10% for the 10 nm CPCs.

Fig. A2 presents two cold start WHTCs with China VI engine #7: the first one without urea injection (Fig. A2a), the second with urea injection (Fig. A2b). For the first case, the highest NO_x emissions (in diluted ppm) are seen at the end of the cycle. For the second case, at the beginning of the cycle, the SCR is cold and thus no urea is injected. Thus for the first 600 s of the cycle the NO_x emissions are similar to the cycle without urea injection. After that point the NO_x concentrations are very low.

Regarding particles, high concentrations can be seen at the beginning of the cycles due to the cold start. The sub-23 nm fraction is high for the first 200 s, but then the SPN >23 nm and SPN >10 nm are quite close to each other. The sub-23 nm cold start particles, based on the literature may be fuel-derived heavy hydrocarbons and/or lubricant-derived ash (Arumugam et al., 2015; Filippo & Maricq, 2008; Giechaskiel, 2020). The absolute cold start levels of the two cycles are different, but this is typical for DPF-equipped engines depending on the preconditioning and the DPF soot load. While for the no urea injection case the particle levels decrease and the SPN >23 nm and >10 nm remain close to each other, for the urea injection case the concentrations start to increase and the difference between >23 nm and >10 nm concentrations also increases. This behavior is characteristic of urea generated particles (Mamakos et al., 2019). Even though the DPF is installed after the SCR, some particles can still pass through the DPF.

Fig. A1. Comparison of the catalytic stripper (CS) and the evaporation tube (ET) systems, both connected at the dilution tunnel. The raw (diluted) signal of the CPC (condensation particle counters) is plotted: (a) SPN >23 nm; (b) SPN >10 nm. Hot start WHTC with China VI engine #6.

Fig. A2. Solid particle number (SPN) emissions measured with the catalytic stripper system at the tailpipe TP(CS) and NO_x emissions measured from the dilution tunnel. Cold start WHTC with engine #7: (a) without urea injection; (b) with urea injection.

Fig. A3 presents a hot start WHTC with engine #7, where the catalytic stripper at the tailpipe was measuring less than half compared to the evaporation tube system at the dilution tunnel. The main reason was the background levels of the dilution tunnel. It should be emphasized that the emission levels were low even with the system at the dilution tunnel ($\text{SPN} > 23 \text{ nm } 9 \times 10^9 \text{ p/kWh}$ and $\text{SPN} > 10 \text{ nm } 2 \times 10^{10} \text{ p/kWh}$).

Fig. A3. Comparison of the catalytic stripper at the tailpipe TP(CS) and the evaporation tube system connected at the dilution tunnel CVS(ET): (a) $\text{SPN} > 23 \text{ nm}$; (b) $\text{SPN} > 10 \text{ nm}$. Hot start WHTC with China VI engine #7.

Fig. 4 presents the $\text{SPN} > 10 \text{ nm}$ emissions for hot WHTCs with engine #2 without (**Fig. A4a**) and with (**Fig. A4b**) the crankcase ventilation connected to the tailpipe. The real time emissions are plotted for the two systems: catalytic stripper at the tailpipe TP(CS) and evaporation tube at the dilution tunnel CVS(ET). The agreement of the two systems is good (25% difference) without crankcase ventilation emissions, but not so good when the crankcase ventilation was connected to the tailpipe (difference 100%). The emissions measured with the TP(CS) system increased almost one order of magnitude: from $2.7 \times 10^{11} \text{ p/kWh}$ to $1.9 \times 10^{12} \text{ p/kWh}$. The differences of the two systems are probably due to the high crankcase emissions and different thermal pre-treatment and counting efficiency at these small sizes. The CVS(ET) system evaporates the volatiles, which subsequently condense on the existing non-volatile particles, while the TP(CS) oxidizes the volatile particles. In addition, due to the direct hot dilution, it minimizes any nucleation and condensation in the first place. Thus the non-volatile particles remain smaller.

Fig. A4. Comparison of the catalytic stripper at the tailpipe TP(CS) and the evaporation tube systems at the dilution tunnel CVS(ET) for SPN > 10 nm. Hot start WHTC with engine #2: (a) the crankcase ventilation was not connected to the tailpipe; (b) The crankcase ventilation was connected downstream of the of the aftertreatment devices, but upstream of the TP(CS) system with a non-heated silicone tube.

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